

Abstract Book

19th International Congress on Anti Cancer Treatment

Presidents

D. Khayat – *Paris, France*

G.N Hortobagyi – *Houston, USA*

Palais des Congrès
Paris, France
February 5-8, 2008

www.icact.com

CONCLUSION

Combination of D and S is manageable with clear evidence of antitumor activity. Preliminary data strongly suggest a new paradigm based on sequential tumor genomic analysis allowing early identification of responders. Early stage DCE-US may predict PFS duration.

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Alpha-tocopheryl succinate (α -TOS) influences cell vitality and enzyme activity in Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells

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One of the most important strategies in research and development of new anticancer agents is the tumor-specific induction of apoptosis. The effects of semisynthetic derivative of vitamin E, (α -TOS, D- α -tocopheryl succinate), appear to be largely restricted to malignant cells, exerting pro-apoptotic tumor-specific activity in vivo and in vitro.

We investigated the in vivo effects of intraperitoneally administered α -TOS on vitality of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells (EAC) in mice, as well as the influence of α -TOS on specific activity of enzymes involved in antioxidative mechanisms in EAC cells.

According to our results, the intraperitoneal application of α -TOS induces the decrease of the EAC vitality, and the statistically significant alteration of the glutathione-dependent enzyme activity in EAC cells, due to the activation of ROS-related apoptotic signaling pathways.

We may conclude that α -TOS is an important micronutrient, with significant impact on vitality and metabolism of malignant cells.

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Fullerenol C60(OH)24 effects on antioxidative enzymes activity in irradiated human erythroleukemia cell line

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Radiotherapy-induced toxicity is a major dose-limiting factor in anti-cancer treatment. Ionizing radiation leads to the formation of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS/RNS) that are associated with radiation-induced cell death. Investigations of fullerenol have provided evidence for its ROS/RNS scavenger properties in vitro and radioprotective efficiency in vivo. Therefore we were interested to evaluate its radioprotective properties in vitro in human erythroleukemia cell line. The number, cell viability and colony-forming capacity of irradiated cells, treated by fullerenol, were not significantly different from non-treated cells, followed by the different response of anti-oxidative enzymes to gamma-radiation induced oxidative stress in cells. Our study provides evidence that the fullerenol exerts increase in activity of anti-oxidative enzymes in irradiated human erythroleukemia cell line K562, acting as an oxygen radical scavenger.

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CYTOPROTECTION By DEXRAZOXANE (DXRz)

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DXRz protects the heart against the cardiotoxicity of doxorubicin without INTERFERING with the antitumour activity of doxorubicin. DXRz also protects the kidney against the nephrotoxicity of doxorubicin in rats and children. Interestingly, ZBINDEN et al have shown that DXRz may protect against the neurotoxicity